

Students' Attitudes toward Statistics, Perceived math Ability, and Instructor's Pedagogy Effect on Grades

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Abstract

It is important to understand students' attitudes toward statistics, their mathematical background, perceptions of the difficulty of the subject, and their evaluation of the value of statistics, because these factors may influence students' performance in statistics courses. The database, The SATS Project, includes students' responses to the Survey of Attitudes Towards Statistics (SATS), students' grades, course information, and instructor characteristics from a national sample of statistics courses collected from 2007 – 2010. In this study, a total of 3,730 university students completed pre- and post-SATS, which gave their expected grades in the course and their attitudes towards various aspects of statistics. Grade expectations vary according to gender. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is used to discover underlying relationships between Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE) questions and fit the model to know how these underlying factors are related to students' grades. Tree-based models (XGBoost, random forests, decision trees) and linear regression perform differently in predicting student grades. We will also see how students' performance differs depending on the teaching models or instructor's teaching methods.

Keywords: Statistics education, Pearson's Chi-squared test, Exploratory Factor Analysis, Prediction models, Students' achievement, Cross Validation, GAISE

1. Introduction

Understanding and addressing student achievement problems is essential for improving educational outcomes and ensuring that all students have the opportunity to succeed. This study utilizes the SATS Project package (<https://github.com/SDSattitudes/SATSdata>), which contains comprehensive data collected from students and instructors between 2007 and 2010. The data, publicly released by Candace Schau and Marjorie Bond and developed into an R package by Douglas Whitaker, includes pre/post student survey responses (the pre-SATS was to be given at anytime from before the course started to at most two weeks after the start, and the post-SATS was to be given ideally before the class ended but could be as early as four weeks before the end), student grades (reported as percentages and letter grades), and detailed instructor and course information, providing a robust foundation for analyzing the factors influencing student achievement. Introductory undergraduate statistics course is critical because it equips students with the ability to analyze and interpret data, developing essential skills for making informed decisions in a variety of academic and professional fields. The Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education (GAISE) is designed for teachers to enhance the teaching and learning of statistics by providing them with best practices and strategies to cultivate statistical literacy, critical thinking, and data-driven decision-making skills in their students, and the GAISE version used here is the 2005 college version (Franklin et al., 2007). Past study compares traditional lecture-based teaching with a flipped classroom approach aligned with updated 2016 version of GAISE guidelines in an introductory statistics course, finding that the flipped method improves student performance and fosters a productive learning mindset (Erhardt & Lim, 2020). Therefore, students taught according to GAISE guidelines performed better than those taught using traditional methods. However, each professor may place different emphasis on different aspects of the GAISE guidelines. Some may emphasize statistical thinking in their classes, while others may focus on using technology for data analysis. Therefore, having the same class taught by different professors may cause a student's attitude toward that class to change. Previous research has shown the fact that 42% to 60% of the variability in motivation and attitudes can be explained by students' perceptions of their instructor's attitude, highlighting the significant influence that instructors have (Wilson 2006). Also, understanding students' attitudes toward statistics and their

impact on learning and achievement is crucial for developing teaching methods that promote positive attitudes, improve academic performance, and encourage a lifelong appreciation for statistical thinking (Hood, Creed, & Neumann, 2012). This study will extend the area of the research to explore the relationship between professors' different emphases and teaching methods, students' different attitudes toward statistics, and student performance.

Objectives of This Study:

The objectives of this study are to investigate the following relationships:

- (a) The relationship between expected and actual grades based on gender.
- (b) The relationship between students' background, aptitude, perceptions toward mathematics and their achievement in the statistics course.
- (c) The relationship between students' various attitudes toward statistics and their achievement in the statistics course.
- (d) The relationship between instructor characteristics and students' achievement.
- (e) The relationship between the varied emphases of professors familiar with the GAISE 2005 guidelines and student performance.

2. Measures

2.1 Samples of students and instructors

The initial dataset comprised 3730 samples collected from students enrolled in various statistics courses (Male = 1457, Female = 2003). The survey contained a question labeled "Level," which asked, "What is the level of this course?" To ensure the analysis was focused and relevant, the dataset was filtered to include only the responses from students who took the "Undergraduate Introductory Statistics" course which reduced the initial 122 sections to 97 sections. Upon examining the 97 sections, we observe that there are multiple repeat instructors. Specifically, several instructors are responsible for teaching multiple courses. For example, Instructor 1 teaches 18 different courses, Instructor 2 teaches 13 courses, and Instructor 24 teaches 10 courses. This is why the number of instructors does not equal the number of sections. Details about repeating instructors can be found in Table A1 in the Appendix.

Since our research primarily focuses on students' grades, rows without grade percentages were excluded, and the eight sections, comprising 418 students, were eliminated because the instructor did not submit grades. Additionally, some students had numeric grade percentages but were assigned grade letter such as "w" for *withdraw*, or *audit*, "np" for *not pass*, or "i" for *incomplete*, or "s" for *satisfactory* were also excluded to align with the study's objectives. After applying these filters, the dataset was reduced from 3726 to 2770 students (Male = 881, Female = 1295) in 97 sections taught by 24 distinct instructors (18 female, 6 male). See Table 1 for details. Since instructors fill out the instructor survey annually, the sums do not add properly since instructors can be promoted from one year to the next.

	Before				After	
	Masters	PhDs	Undergraduate		Masters	PhDs
Adjuncts/Staffs	5	2	1	Adjuncts/Staffs	4	2
Asst professors	1	9	0	Asst professors	1	7
Assoc Professors	1	8	0	Assoc Professors	1	5
Full Professors	0	8	0	Full Professors	0	6

Table1: Distribution of Instructors' Degrees and Ranks Before and After Filtering

2.2 Student background, aptitude, perceptions

Schibeci and Riley demonstrated a significant causal relationship where perceptions of science instruction influenced attitudes, which subsequently affected achievement (Schibeci & Riley, 1986). There are also other perceptions of the class that can influence outcomes, such as

confidence. Students' background and aptitude are also important, as they provide a basis for the new knowledge that students acquire and may also influence students' achievement in a course.

Included in the SATS-36 there are several questions to measure global identity, the Pre- and Post-SATS have these questions with the variable name in parenthesis, (1) How good at mathematics are you? (cgmth), (2) If the field in which you hope to be employed when you finish school, how much will you use statistics? (vcareer), and (3) How confident are you that you can (have) master(ed) introductory statistics material? (cmaster). The Pre-SATS asks (4) How well did you do in mathematics courses you have taken in the past? (PriorMath) and (5a) If the choice had been yours, how likely is it that you would have chosen to take any course in statistics? (takeany), and the Post-SATS also includes (5b) If you could, how likely is it that you would choose to take another course in statistics? (ptakemore). These questions are measured on a 7-point scale with anchors that are relevant to the question. For example, question 5b would have a one as not at all likely and seven as very likely.

2.3 Survey of Attitudes Toward Statistics

Assessing attitudes can offer valuable insights for both students and instructors, as well as serving to evaluate the success of various curricula and teaching methods (Vanhoof, Kuppens, Sotos, Verschaffel, & Onghena, 2011). The Survey of Attitudes Toward Statistics (SATS-36; Schau, 2003) is used to assess participants' attitudes toward statistics and is comprised of six subscales, Affect (6 items), Cognitive Competence (6 items), Value (6 items), Difficulty (7 items), Interest (4 items) and Effort (4 items). Each subscale is the average of items that can get to know students accurately about these subscales. Participants rated thirty-six items using the scales with 1 = Strongly Disagree to 7 = Strongly Agree. The Affect subscale measures positive and negative feelings toward statistics. The Cognitive Competence subscale measures participants' attitudes regarding their perception of their ability to mentally comprehend statistics. The Value subscale measures participants' perceptions of the usefulness and worth of statistics. The Difficulty (perceived easiness) subscale is measured by items which collectively asked about participants' attitudes regarding how difficult statistics was. For all the subscales except for difficulty, higher values mean a strong agreement to the subscale; however high difficulty values indicate that the student perceives the class as easy. The Interest subscale measured how much interest a participant has in statistics. The Effort subscale measures the student's effort over the course of the class. However, due to significant ceiling effects and declines in Effort scores from pre-course to post-course observed across various studies, interpreting these scores to reflect changes in attitudes toward statistics is challenging; thus, researchers should consider reporting only descriptive statistics or using nonparametric methods for the Effort scale to avoid violations of normality assumptions in their analyses (Whitaker, Unfried, & Bond, 2022). Descriptive statistics toward 6 subscales can be seen in Figure 1. Therefore, in this study, we will not use the subscale Effort.

Figure 1: Comparison of Pre-Course (left) and Post-Course (right) Subscale Distributions in SATS-36 Instrument

2.4 Varied Emphasis and Teaching Methods of Professors

Each instructor indicated their teaching methods related to GAISE (Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education) by answering 10 questions using the scales with 1 = Never, 5 = Almost every time (Franklin et al., 2007). Questions details can be found in Table A2 in the Appendix.

2.5 Grades

Each student indicated their anticipated final grade twice: once in the pre-SATS and once during the post-SATS. Students indicated their anticipated final grade using the scale: A+, A, A-, B+, B, B-, C+, C, C-, D+, D, D-, F. To compare to the actual grades, these student's grades were converted into numerical values based on a 4-point scale (e.g., A+ = 4.00, A = 3.67, A- = 3.33, etc.), referred to as the "4.0 Scale Method". Additionally, grades were also categorized into broader groups where A+, A, and A- were grouped as 'A'; B+, B, and B- as 'B'; C+, C, and C- as 'C'; and the rest were classified as 'Not Pass'. This grouping method is referred to as the "Ordinal Grouping Method" and was used to facilitate ordinal logistic regression analysis.

Instructors report students' actual grades in two forms: percentage and letter grade. These final grades reported by instructors provide a comprehensive measure of students' performance in the course. For some analyses, we use percentage grades.

Furthermore, there were inconsistencies in how teachers assigned letter grades to percentage scores. For example, some teachers might assign a letter grade of "C" for a 50%, while another might assign an "F." The distribution of inconsistent grade can be found in Figure A1 in the Appendix. Letter grades can be transferred among schools and used for graduation requirements, but numeric scores are inconsistent. This is why we limit our use of the numeric scores in favor of the letter grades, but we encourage future researchers to further explore the numeric grades since it is unusual to have data with both numeric and letter grades.

3. Results

3.1 The relationship between expected and actual grades based on gender

To ensure the accuracy of the analysis, we prepared the data by first handling missing values and then converting the expected grades into a numeric format based on a 4.0 Scale Method. The dataset contained 589 missing values of expected grade out of 2770 total data points, approximately 21% of the data. Because each student will estimate the expected score based on their perceived understanding of the material, their liking for the course, and other individual factors, the expected grades are subjective. Therefore, we excluded entries with missing expected grade data to ensure the integrity and accuracy of our analysis, including only students with complete information about their expectations. Both pre-expected grades and post-expected grades were considered. Chi-squared test was applied to explore any significant associations in how male and female students assess their performance relative to their actual outcomes, providing insights into any gender-based differences in grade expectation accuracy. We calculated the percentages of accurate, overestimated, and underestimated grade expectations for male and female students. Specifically, "overestimated" indicates that students predicted a higher grade than they achieved, while "underestimated" reflects a prediction lower than the actual grade received. An "accurate" expectation means the predicted grade matched the actual grade. To analyze the relationship between expected and actual grades based on gender, we employed two different grading methods. Method 1: 4.0 Scale

Grades were converted to a 4.0 scale (e.g., A+ = 4.0, A = 3.67, A- = 3.33, etc.).

Method 2: Ordinal Grouping

Grades were grouped into broader categories: A+, A, and A- were grouped as A (3.67), B+, B, and B- as B (2.67), C+, C, and C- as C (1.67), D+, D, and D- as D (0.67), and F as 0.

Regarding to the pre-expected grades, for the 4.0 Scale Method and Ordinal Grouping Method, females had a higher percentage of underestimations and accuracy (15.44%, 26.41%; 7.34%, 46.33%, respectively) than males (10.10%, 19.98%; 5.90%, 37.46%, respectively), and males had a higher percentage of overestimations (69.92%; 56.64, respectively) than females (58.15%; 48.33%, respectively), ($X^2(2)=31.929$; $X^2(2)=22.288$, respectively), with both have $P<0.01$.

Regarding to the post-expected grades, for the 4.0 Scale Method and Ordinal Grouping Method, females had a higher percentage of underestimations (26.72%; 10.50%, respectively) than males (21.23%; 8.74%, respectively), males had a higher percentage of overestimations (42.34%;25.08%, respectively) than the females (35.52%; 21.85%, respectively), and females and males had almost same accuracy (37.76%, 36.44%; 67.64, 66.17%, respectively), ($X^2(2)=13.069$; $X^2(2)=4.196$, respectively), with $p<0.01$ and $p>0.1$.

The data reveals that female students have higher underestimation rates compared to male students on both of pre- and post-expected grades. One possible explanation for this pattern is that female students may exhibit more caution in their self-assessments, leading to more conservative grade expectations and thus a higher likelihood of underestimating their performance.

Conversely, male students exhibit a higher rate of overestimation compared to female students. This tendency could be attributed to greater confidence or optimism among male students regarding their academic abilities, leading them to expect higher grades than they ultimately achieve. This overconfidence might reflect a broader societal tendency for males to perceive themselves as stronger or more capable in competitive scenarios, which in this context translates into higher expected grades.

We can also see from the data that, for both males and females, the post-expected grades are more accurate than the pre-expected grades. This may be because more than 700 students already knew their actual grades when filling in the post-expected grades. It may also be because students can know their understanding of the course through regular exams and homework grades at the end of the course, so they can better estimate their final grades.

3.2 The relationship between students' perceptions toward mathematics, background, aptitude, and their achievement in the statistics course.

We conducted a model comparison analysis to analyze the relationship between students' background, aptitude, perceptions toward mathematics and their achievement in the statistics course. We split the data into training (70%) and testing (30%) sets, ensuring that the model could be trained on one subset and validated on another. For the next step, we used three tree-based models (Random Forest, Decision Tree, and XGBoost) and Ordinal Logistic Regression to analyze the relationship. Each model was trained using a 10-fold cross-validation strategy to ensure robust performance evaluation.

The reason for using this approach is to ensure a robust analysis by leveraging the strengths of both models. Tree-based models are well suited for identifying complex patterns in data because they can capture complex nonlinear relationships and interactions between variables. Ordinal logistic regression captures linear relationships and serves as a baseline for comparison with more complex tree-based models. The comparison summarized in Table 2 allowed us to know decision tree model best captures the relationship between the predictors and student achievement in the statistics course.

Model	Accuracy
Ordinal Logistic Regression	0.4237968
Random Forest	0.3890374
Decision Tree	0.4518717
XGBoost	0.3582888

Table 2: Model Performance Comparison

Variable importance analysis based on decision tree model revealed that PriorMath (34.73) was the most influential predictor, followed by Pre.cgmath (21.90), Pre.cmaster (11.62), Pre.vcareer (4.86), and takeany (3.89). These findings underscore the significance of prior mathematical knowledge and cognitive competence in predicting student grades, highlighting areas for targeted educational interventions. The bar plot shown in Figure 2 below illustrates the distribution of grades across different levels of prior math experience. Each bar represents a different prior math level and is segmented by grade categories: A, B, C, and NotPass. The plot reveals a clear trend: as prior math levels increase, the proportion of students achieving an A grade rises significantly, while the proportion of C and NotPass grades decreases. Specifically, students with stronger mathematical backgrounds tend to perform better in the statistics course. For more details on how these predictors interact and influence student grades, a decision tree plot was made in Figure 3. The decision tree model's "C" and "NotPass" categories aren't purposefully excluded; rather, their absence results from the model's splitting criteria and feature importance. Despite our efforts to balance the dataset and adjust model parameters, the features used in the analysis may not provide enough distinction between "C", "NotPass", and the other categories. In this dataset, grade B is the most frequent grade among all observations, so the root node predicts grade B for all students. The root node classifies the data based on PriorMath, scores below 6 are most likely to get a predicted grade of B. For students with PriorMath scores of 6 or higher, the tree performs another split on $\text{PriorMath} \geq 7$ and predicts a grade of A. For students with PriorMath scores between 6 and 7, the tree is further split by Pre.cmaster, with scores above 7 predicted as A and scores below 7 predicted as B. While Pre.cgmath is generally a highly influential predictor, in this particular tree structure, Pre.cmaster offered a more immediate refinement of predictions following the initial PriorMath split.

Figure 2: Distribution of Grades Across Prior Math Levels

Figure 3: Decision tree plot with students' background, aptitude, and perceptions toward mathematics predictors

3.3 The relationship between students' various attitudes toward statistics and their achievement in the statistics course.

Using the previously described methods, the relationship between students' various attitudes toward statistics and their achievement in the statistics course was analyzed. See Table 3 for model comparisons detail.

Model	Accuracy
Ordinal Logistic Regression	0.4005602
Random Forest	0.3543417
Decision Tree	0.3865546
XGBoost	0.3557423

Table 3: Model Performance Comparison

After determining that Ordinal Logistic Regression is the most accurate model among the three tree-based models (Random Forest, Decision Tree, and XGBoost), we further analyzed the influence of various predictors on student achievement in the statistics course by examining odds ratios derived from the model coefficients. The coefficient for Pre.Affect is 0.1028223, with an odds ratio of 1.1082945, indicating that an increase in Pre.Affect is associated with approximately a 10.8% increase in the odds of achieving a higher grade, however, this effect is not statistically significant (p-value = 0.09863195). Higher cognitive competence (Pre.CogComp) significantly increases the odds of achieving higher grades, with an odds ratio of 1.171 (p-value = 0.0132), indicating that greater cognitive competence is associated with a 17.1% increase in the likelihood of achieving a higher grade. Pre.Value also shows a significant positive effect, with a coefficient of 0.3214790 and an odds ratio of 1.3791660 (p-value = 3.926809e-09), indicating that an increase in the perceived value of the subject raises the odds of achieving a higher grade by approximately 37.9%. Higher Pre.Diff also increases the odds of achieving a higher grade, with an odds ratio of 1.158 (p-value = 0.0227), indicating a 15.8% increase. Conversely, Pre.Interest has a significant negative effect, with a coefficient of -0.1775013 and an odds ratio of 0.8373599 (p-value = 8.595746e-05), indicating that greater interest in the subject decreases the odds of achieving a higher grade by approximately 16.3%. The threshold coefficients represent the log odds boundaries between adjacent levels. The transition threshold from NotPass to C is 0.184, which represents the logical value of the change in the probability of belonging to the Fail category versus the C category. The transition threshold from C to B is 1.747, which indicates that a higher logit value is required to transition from C to B. Finally, the transition threshold from B to A is 3.447, which is the highest logit value and reflects the largest change required to obtain an A grade.

These findings show the importance of students' attitudes in their academic performance. The robust performance of the ordinal logistic regression model emphasizes its value in capturing complex, multi-category relationships in educational data.

3.4 The relationship between instructor characteristics and students' achievement.

To determine whether the characteristics of teachers, such as gender and degree, affect student performance, we conducted Welch Two Sample t-tests for each characteristic due to the variances and the sample sizes of the two groups for instructors' sex (n=1967 for students with a female instructor and n=748 for students with a male instructor) and instructors' degrees are significantly different (n=398 for students with an instructor holding a Master's degree and n=2317 for students with an instructor holding a PhD degree.).

A Welch Two Sample t-test for InstructorSex showed no significant difference in student grades between male and female instructors (t = 0.37469, df = 1168.8, p-value = 0.708), indicating that the instructor's sex does not significantly influence student grades. The mean grade percent for male instructors was 81.07, while for female instructors it was 80.84.

A Welch Two Sample t-test for Degree indicated no significant difference in student grades based on the instructor's degree ($t = -1.8637$, $df = 490.46$, $p\text{-value} = 0.06296$). The mean grade percent for instructors with one degree was 79.69, while for those with another degree it was 81.23.

These findings while not significant are what students and their instructors would want to observe – no difference in student grades based on the instructor's degree or gender.

3.5 The relationship between the varied emphases of professors familiar with the GAISE 2005 guidelines and student performance.

To investigate the relationship between the varied emphases of professors familiar with the GAISE guidelines and student performance, we first conducted a factor analysis on variables related to different aspects of the GAISE guidelines to explore the underlying structure. See Table A2 for variables details. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was then performed, resulting in a significant p-value ($X^2(45) = 19691.11$), $p < 0.001$), indicating the data's suitability for factor analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test further confirmed this with an overall MSA of 0.78, though "EvalStuLearn" had a lower MSA (0.21) and was subsequently removed from the analysis.

After removing "EvalStuLearn", we performed Bartlett's Test and the KMO test again. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity showed significant results ($X^2(36) = 17288.6$), $p < 0.001$), indicating that the correlation matrix was not an identity matrix and that the variables were interrelated, thus confirming the appropriateness of factor analysis. The KMO test yielded an improved overall MSA of 0.85, indicating that the dataset was now even more suitable for factor analysis.

Next, a screen and parallel analysis was generated in Figure 4 to determine there are 3 factors to retain. These three factors represented different dimensions of the GAISE guidelines: MR1 (Conceptual ideas with active learning), MR2 (Technologies to analyze data in context), and MR3 (Students learning with communication and assessments). See Figure 5 for details.

Figure 4: Screen and Parallel Analysis Plot for Factor Determination

Figure 5: Factor Analysis Diagram Showing Loadings on MR1, MR2, and MR3

For the next step, an ordinal logistic regression model was employed. The response variable, Grade.Category, was derived from the students' final letter grades and categorized into four groups: A, B, C and Not Pass using the Ordinal Grouping Method. The predictors included three factors (MR1, MR2, MR3) obtained from exploratory factor analysis. The ordinal logistic regression model revealed significant relationships between the factors and student grade categories. The coefficients for MR1, MR2, and MR3 were all positive and statistically significant, indicating that higher emphasis on these factors was associated with higher grade categories. Specifically, see Table 4 for detail.

Predictor	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p-value	Odds ratio
MR1	0.15613	0.03990	3.913	< 0.001	1.17
MR2	0.26286	0.03934	6.683	< 0.001	1.3
MR3	0.12129	0.03980	3.047	0.00231	1.13

Table 4: Summary of Ordinal Logistic Regression Results for Predictors MR1, MR2, and MR3

A one-unit increase in the emphasis on conceptual ideas with active learning (MR1) is associated with 1.17 times higher odds of achieving a higher grade. A one-unit increase in the use of technologies to analyze data in context (MR2) is associated with 1.30 times higher odds of achieving a higher grade. A one-unit increase in fostering student learning through communication and assessments (MR3) is associated with 1.13 times higher odds of achieving a higher grade.

In our ordinal logistic regression model, the threshold coefficients indicate the logit boundaries that separate different grade categories: -2.19383 for NotPass|C, -0.75063 for C|B, and 0.86608 for B|A. A instructor whose combined factor score is less than -2.19383 is more likely to have students in the "NotPass" category. A score greater than -2.19383 but less than -0.75063 is more likely to fall in the "C" category. A student whose combined factor score is between -0.75063 and 0.86608 is more likely to be in the "B" category. A instructor whose combined factor score is greater than 0.86608 is more likely to have students in the "A" category.

From the results above, we determined that all three factors significantly influence student performance, with the *use of technologies for data analysis* showing the strongest impact. This may indicate the importance of incorporating modern teaching strategies in statistics education to improve student achievement.

4. Future Research

Because we have very valuable grade percentages in this dataset, and we also know which students have withdrawn from the course, future research can delve into which kind of students are more likely to withdraw from the course. For example, whether they are not interested in the corresponding major of the course, or whether they choose to withdraw because of the teacher's teaching methods and other reasons. This type of research can help schools better understand the reasons why students withdraw from the course, so as to improve the curriculum and teaching methods and enhance the students' learning experience. Also future research can be more focused on the nested effect between the instructors.

Since some subjective questions related to students' attitudes toward statistics have missing values, future research can explore whether the answers to these subjective questions can be inferred from other data of the students. By using data inference methods, these missing values can be filled in, thereby obtaining more accurate research results. This method can not only enhance the integrity of the data, but also provide a more reliable analysis basis, which helps to more comprehensively understand students' attitudes toward statistics and their influencing factors.

5. Conclusion

This study revealed which factors are positively correlated with the final grades obtained, which factors are negatively correlated with the final grades, and the extent to which these factors affect the final grades. Although not all the results shown by the data are what we expected, for example, a high interest in statistics does not guarantee good grades in statistics courses, and there is no completely proportional relationship between the two. However, the results also show that the better the student's perception of their previous performance in mathematics classes, the greater the possibility of getting good grades in statistics courses, which is consistent with our expectations. In addition, the focus of the teacher's teaching method also affects student performance. Compared with focusing on conceptual ideas with active learning and promoting student learning through communication and assessment, focusing on technologies to analyze data in context is more conducive to students getting good grades. Lastly, there was not a significant difference in students' grades based on instructor's gender or degree. Through this study, educators can better understand the key factors that affect student performance, thereby optimizing teaching methods and improving students' academic performance.

References

- Erhardt, E. B., & Lim, W. (2020, May 31). Effects of a GAISE-based teaching method on students' learning in introductory statistics. *Communications for Statistical Applications and Methods*. The Korean Statistical Society. <https://doi.org/10.29220/csam.2020.27.3.269>
- Franklin, C., Kader, G., Mewborn, D., Moreno, J., Peck, R., Perry, M., & Scheaffer, R. (2007). Guidelines for assessment and instruction in statistics education (GAISE) report.
- Hood, M., Creed, P. A., & Neumann, D. L. (2012). Using the expectancy value model of motivation to understand the relationship between student attitudes and achievement in statistics. *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 11(2), 72-85.
- Schau, C. (2003). Survey of Attitudes Toward Statistics (SATS-36). In S. Vanhoof, S. Kuppens, A. E. Castro Sotos, L. Verschaffel, & P. Onghena (Eds.), *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.52041/serj.v10i1.354>
- Schibeci, R.A. and Riley, J.P., II (1986), Influence of students' background and perceptions on science attitudes and achievement. *J. Res. Sci. Teach.*, 23: 177-187. <https://doi-org.ezaccess.libraries.psu.edu/10.1002/tea.3660230302>
- Vanhoof, S., Kuppens, S., Sotos, A. E. C., Verschaffel, L., & Onghena, P. (2011). Measuring statistics attitudes: Structure of the survey of attitudes toward statistics (SATS-36). *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 10(1), 35-51.
- Whitaker, D., Unfried, A., & Bond, M. (2022). Challenges associated with measuring attitudes using the SATS family of instruments. *Statistics Education Research Journal*, 21(1).
- Wilson, J. H. (2006). Predicting student attitudes and grades from perceptions of instructors' attitudes. *Teaching of Psychology*, 33(2), 91-95.

Appendix

InstructorID	Courses
1	1 1, 2, 11, 12, 37, 38, 48, 49, 82, 83, 97, 98, 108, 109
2	2 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 28, 29, 30, 71, 72, 94, 95, 120, 121
3	3 8, 9
4	8 18, 19, 60, 61, 125, 126
5	9 20, 21, 22, 58, 84, 113, 114
6	10 23, 24, 25
7	11 26, 27, 56, 57
8	12 31
9	13 32, 101, 105
10	14 33, 34
11	15 35, 36
12	19 50
13	23 64
14	24 67, 68, 87, 88, 89, 134, 135, 136, 137
15	25 69
16	26 70, 92, 93, 104, 110, 111, 112
17	29 76, 77
18	31 65, 66, 132, 133, 141
19	32 78, 79, 80
20	36 103
21	37 116, 117
22	38 118, 119
23	39 122, 123
24	40 124

Table A1: Distribution of Course Sections by Instructor

Variable	Variable Description
StatLit	Emphasizing statistical literacy
StatThink	Emphasizing statistical thinking
DataContext	Using data in a meaningful context
Concept	Incorporating Stressing conceptual understanding
ActLearn	Incorporating Fostering active learning
TechData	Incorporating Using technology for data analysis
TechConcept	Incorporating Using technology to develop conceptual understanding
EvalStuLearn	Incorporating Using assessments to evaluate student learning
ImprStuLearn	Incorporating Using assessments to improve student learning
Communication	Incorporating Emphasizing student communication of their statistical understanding

Table A2: questions related to GAISE

Figure A1: Distribution of Grade Percentages with Inconsistencies